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ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC FILMS OBTAINED FROM GELATIN

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Abstract: *In this study, the effect of plasticizers on the formation of thermoplastic gelatin films and their physico-mechanical properties was investigated. By adding plasticizers into the gelatin matrix, thermoplastic behavior was imparted, allowing the films to be processed using conventional plastic manufacturing methods. For this purpose, water and glycerol were selected as plasticizers and introduced into the gelatin matrix in various ratios, with glycerol content reaching up to 100%. Film samples with different compositions were prepared and their physico-mechanical characteristics were examined. The results demonstrated that increasing glycerol content led to a decrease in mechanical strength, an increase in elongation at break, and a reduction in Young's modulus. Thus, it was confirmed that the properties of thermoplastic gelatin films can be controlled by adjusting the plasticizer content.*

Keywords: *Thermoplastic gelatin, glycerin, water, film, physical and mechanical properties.*

Introduction

Most of the polymers used today are synthetic, and their biological suitability and biodegradability are very limited compared to biopolymers such as proteins and lipids. Biopolymer-based films show a promising potential to replace oil-based plastic films to reduce environmental impact. [1] The characteristics of films based on biopolymers are mainly determined by the chemical nature of the biopolymer. Protein-based films have good organoleptic and mechanical properties, and also serve as a good barrier against non-condensable gases (O₂, CO₂ and N₂) and aromas [2].

The mechanism of gelatin formation is formed by the sequence of junctions of gelatin chains, forming thermionically reversible networks by joining spirals in the stabilized junction zones of collagen with hydrogen bonds associated with conformational disruption [3-6]. When treating gelatin, i.e., transferring it to a thermoplastic state, water [7: 8], glycerin [9: 10], sorbitol [11], and many other plasticizers were used, which in turn affects the physical-mechanical, thermal, water-related, and other properties of gelatin [12-16]. Thermoplastic gelatin films [17] have gained considerable attention due to their use in various fields, including food packaging, pharmaceuticals, and biomedical devices. Gelatin, a natural protein derived from collagen [18], possesses unique properties such as biological compatibility, biodegradability, and the ability to form a perfect film. These properties make gelatin a promising candidate for the development of environmentally friendly and sustainable packaging solutions. The physical and mechanical properties of thermoplastic gelatin films, such as mechanical strength, tensile strength, and modulus of rupture, play a decisive role in determining their suitability for specific products. Understanding these characteristics is crucial for optimizing the conditions for forming and processing to achieve the desired performance characteristics.

In this article, film samples were obtained by changing the ratio of plasticizers for obtaining thermoplastic gelatin films and their physical and mechanical properties were analyzed. The goal is to provide an understanding of the problems associated with thermoplastic gelatin films by studying the relationship between formation, processing techniques, and resulting properties.

Materials and research methods

Materials

The research was conducted in 2025-2026 at the Laboratory of Nanostructured Composite Polymer Materials of the Institute of Polymer Chemistry and Physics within the framework of the scientific project "Functional, including nanostructured polymer composite materials."

Gelatin (Gel) (GOST 11293-2017) - cattle gelatin grade p-200 produced by the company OAO "MOJELIT," $\rho = 1.3 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Glycerol $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ (GOST 6824-96), colorless liquid, $M=92.094 \text{ g/mol}$, $T_q=290 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\rho=1260 \text{ kg/m}^3$. Water distilled H_2O , $\rho=1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Method for obtaining thermoplastic gelatin film

To obtain thermoplastic gelatin films, distilled water is weighed in a beaker using scales and added to the water weighed relative to the gelatin to which glycerin is added, then mixed and gelatin is added, mixed, then placed in a furnace at 80°C and mixed with a mixer for 2 hours, then poured onto a surface made of Teflon corresponding to the concentration of the prepared solution. The drying time lasts up to 2 days, depending on the room temperature. After drying, the film samples are separated from Teflon, the film sample is transparent and in a flexible state. Figure 1.

a) **Fig. 1.** Gelatin with 30% glycerin content, a) film (size $20 \times 30 \text{ cm}$) and b) package samples (size $18 \times 25 \text{ cm}$)

Mechanical analyses

Tension tests were conducted at Shimadzu AG-X PLUS (Japan) in accordance with the international standard ASTM D 638. To measure the modulus of tensile strength (E), tests were conducted at a rate of 1 mm/min to a deformation of 0.3%, after which tests were conducted at a rate of 20 mm/min to measure the stress of transition to a fluid state (σ) and deformation (ϵ).

Results and discussion

The production of thermoplastic gelatin films involves modifications of the gelatin matrix to demonstrate thermoplastic behavior, which allows the material to be processed using traditional plastic production methods. This modification usually involves the introduction of plasticizers to increase the material's flexibility, physical-mechanical and thermal stability. Plasticizers are low-volatility molecules that are added to biopolymer materials, allowing to change the functional properties of films by increasing their elongation, flexibility, flexibility, elasticity, hardness, and mechanical properties [19].

The effect of plasticizers is more pronounced in the mechanical properties of the material. With an increase in the amount of glycerin in the gelatin composition, its relative elongation is significantly affected, and it was found that the elongation at break increases up to 120% with the introduction of 50% glycerin into the composition. Physically, as the ratio of plasticizers increases, plasticizers enter the chains, reducing the interaction between the chains of gelatin, increasing the mobility between them, and therefore the viscosity decreases.

In this work, film samples were obtained and their physical and mechanical properties were studied by introducing glycerin into the gelatin composition in various proportions during the transfer of gelatin to the thermoplastic state.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 2. Changes in physical and mechanical properties, mechanical stress (a), Young's modulus (b), and relative elongation (c) with an increase in the proportion of glycerin in gelatin

When studying the mechanical properties of the film samples, it was found that with an increase in the amount of glycerin in the gelatin, the mechanical stress and Young's modulus decrease, but the relative elongation increases. When comparing the values of samples obtained with the addition of 100% glycerin with the values of gelatin films obtained without the addition of glycerin, it was found that the mechanical stress decreased from 41.8 MPa to 6.5 MPa, Young's modulus from 1134 MPa to 22.4 MPa, and the relative elongation increased from 9% to 245%. In the process of physical interaction, the interaction of gelatin chains with each other decreases, and glycerin establishes hydrogen bonds between the chains, and this interaction is carried out through glycerin, which increases their plastic properties and transitions to a flexible thermoplastic state. Excessive glycerin content between chains serves as lubrication in the material, resulting in increased relative displacement of chains, therefore relative elongation increases and strength decreases. The main interactions between gelatin and glycerin are that the carbonyl, amino, and hydroxyl groups of gelatin bind with the hydroxyl groups of glycerin, influencing the plasticity of the structure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study showed that the addition of different concentrations of glycerin affects the properties of the gelatin film of cattle skin. All the conducted measurements showed a significant influence on the physical and mechanical properties with an increase in the concentration of glycerin, which led to a decrease in the values of mechanical stress and Young's modulus, an increase in relative elongation. The effect of the plasticizer was observed in the mechanical properties when the glycerin content in gelatin exceeded 20%. It was possible to obtain packages from thermoplastic gelatin films containing 30% glycerin.

REFERENCES

1. Mariniello, L., Di Pierro, P., Esposito, C., Sorrentino, A., Masi, P., & Porta, R. (2003). Preparation and mechanical properties of edible pectin–soy flour films obtained in the absence or presence of transglutaminase. *Journal of Biotechnology*, 102, 191–198.
2. Fabra, M. J., Hambleton, A., Talens, P., Debeaufort, F., Chiralt, A., & Voilley, A. (2008). Aroma barrier properties of sodium caseinate-based films. *Biomacromolecules*, 9, 1406–1410.
3. Pezron I, Djabourov M, Leblond J. Conformation of gelatin chains in aqueous solutions: 1. A light and small angle neutron scattering study. *Polymer* 1991;32:3201–10.
4. Ross-Murphy SB. Structure and rheology of gelatin gels: recent progress. *Polymer* 1992;33:2622–7.
5. Maquet J, Theveneau H, Djabourov M, Leblond J, Papon P. ! State of water in gelatin solutions and gels: an 1 h n.m.r investigation. *Polymer* 1986;27:1103–10.
6. Michon C, Cuvelier G, Relkin P, Launay B. Influence of thermal history on the stability of gelatin gels. *Int J Biol Macromol* 1997;20:259–64.
7. Sobral P. J. A., Menegalli F. C., Guilbert S. Phase transitions of bovine hide gelatin plasticized by water //Proceedings. – 1998.
8. Pinhas M. F. et al. The effect of water on the physicochemical and mechanical properties of gelatin //Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry. – 1996. – Т. 47. – №. 5. – С. 1499-1511.
9. Tapia-Blácido D. R., do Amaral Sobral P. J., Menegalli F. C. Effect of drying conditions and plasticizer type on some physical and mechanical properties of amaranth flour films //LWT-Food Science and Technology. – 2013. – Т. 50. – №. 2. – С. 392-400.
10. Lukasik K. V., Ludescher R. D. Molecular mobility in water and glycerol plasticized cold-and hot-cast gelatin films //Food Hydrocolloids. – 2006. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 96-105.
11. Menegalli F. C. et al. Characteristics of gelatin biofilms in relation to drying process conditions near melting //Drying Technology. – 1999. – Т. 17. – №. 7-8. – С. 1697-1706.
12. Sobral P. J. A. et al. Mechanical, water vapor barrier and thermal properties of gelatin based edible films //Food hydrocolloids. – 2001. – Т. 15. – №. 4-6. – С. 423-432.
13. Vanin F. M. et al. Effects of plasticizers and their concentrations on thermal and functional properties of gelatin-based films //Food Hydrocolloids. – 2005. – Т. 19. – №. 5. – С. 899-907.
14. Ugli N. N. F., Rustamovich A. N. Perspective Chapter: Morphological and Thermal Properties of Biodegradable Graft Copolymer LLDPE-g-MA/Gelatin Composites //Polyethylene-New Developments and Applications. – IntechOpen, 2024.
15. Normurodov N. F. U. et al. Mechanical properties of biodegradable composites based on polyethylene and gelatin //Science and Innovative Development. - 2022. - Vol. 5. - No. 5. - P. 5-12.
16. Normurodov N. F. U. et al. Degradation features of polyethylene and gelatin compositions
17. Suderman N., Isa M. I. N., Sarbon N. M. The effect of plasticizers on the functional properties of biodegradable gelatin-based film: A review //Food bioscience. – 2018. – Т. 24. – С. 111-119.
18. Gómez-Guillén M. C. et al. Functional and bioactive properties of collagen and gelatin from alternative sources: A review //Food hydrocolloids. – 2011. – Т. 25. – №. 8. – С. 1813-1827.
19. Hanani Z. A. N., Roos Y. H., Kerry J. P. Use and application of gelatin as potential biodegradable packaging materials for food products //International journal of biological macromolecules. – 2014. – Т. 71. – С. 94-102.